

Qualitative and quantitative characteristics of organic extract from plant materials used in lentil cultivation

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Phytocenoses create significantly more primary organic matter, which determines the genesis and, as a consequence, soil fertility, than agrocenoses. Since they form a phytomass with a closed cycle of substances, including a variety of plant material, while in an agrophytocenosis a person takes the bulk of the plant matter with the harvest, and the remaining part is insignificant, and the production process itself depends on the genetic nature of the crop, technological processes, weather conditions, provision of the soil with moisture reserves, nutrients [1]. Organic preparations used in agriculture are promising and in demand. The purpose of the research is a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the extract from plant raw materials that allows compensating for the organic matter necessary in the agrophytocenosis, due to the plant extract of the phytocenosis. The studies were conducted in the chernozem zone of the arid and moderately arid steppe of Altai. The object of the research was green plant extracts of phytocenoses, which were used in the cultivation of lentils and other crops as stimulants and growth regulators. Previously, laboratory studies were conducted in lysimeters using a hardware and software complex that allows online monitoring of such parameters in the soil as temperature, humidity, environmental reaction, mobile nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium [2]. In the production experiment, to regulate growth processes, the plant extract was added during sowing and according to the developed foliar feeding scheme. The quality of the plant extract and its effectiveness for the agrocenosis is determined by a set of factors that affect the completeness and speed of extraction of active substances. The fundamental factor should be considered the component composition, which in the study area in the spring consisted of 80-90% cereals, 10-20% legumes and cruciferous plants, over time, the qualitative composition of the phytocenosis changed, but insignificantly. An important tool in the preparation of the plant extract is grinding green plants, in laboratory conditions, the plant material was chopped to 5-10 cm, and in the production experiment, the plant mass was mown with a combine. A qualitative assessment was carried out in an accredited laboratory using methods for determining organic compounds in plant extracts. It was found that the reaction of the medium is mainly acidic, slightly acidic, sometimes neutral, the carbon content is in the range from 300 g / l to 450 g / l, sugar - 0.1-9.0 g / l, dry residue 1.2-6.2 g / l. The content of macroelements is: total nitrogen - 0.1-1.5 g / l; phosphorus - 0.1-1.0 g / l; potassium - 0.9-5.8 g / l, mesoelements and microelements are present in slightly larger quantities. The content of plant extract depends not only on the component composition of plant mass, but also the extraction mode, the ratio of raw materials and extractant. This approach allows for the saturation of agrocenoses with the necessary nutrients, using extracts of the neighboring phytocenosis.

References

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